

D 7.2

Report on Dissemination, Communication and networking activities

UnitelmaSapienza
università degli studi di Roma

Funded by
the European Union

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

@STAR4BBS

D 7.2

Report on Dissemination, Communication and networking activities

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

M34 ---- 30/06/2025

WORK PACKAGE

WP7

LEADER

APRE

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU

AUTHORS

Valeria Mingardi
Ilaria Bientinesi

Programme

HORIZON
EUROPE

Grant agreement

101060588

Start

Sept.2022

Duration

36 Months

Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
ILARIA BIENTINESI	APRE
VALERIA MINGARDI	APRE

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
LUANA LADU	TUB
NIKOLA MATOVIC	TUB

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	20/06/2025	Ilaria Bientinesi	First draft
0.2	22/06/2025	Valeria Mingardi	First review
0.3	22/06/2025	Luana Ladu	First review by TUB
0.4	26/06/2025	Nikola Matovic	Second review by TUB
0.5	27/06/2025	Valeria Mingardi; Ilaria Bientinesi	Implementation of TUB suggestions
1.0	30/06/2025	Valeria Mingardi; Ilaria Bientinesi	First version released

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Index of Contents

1	Introduction.....	8
1.1	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Strategy	9
1.2	Communication Activities	9
1.3	Dissemination Activities.....	10
2	STAR4BBS Communication Activities.....	11
2.1	Development of Visual Communication Materials.....	11
2.2	WEBSITE.....	12
2.3	WEBSITE metrics	14
2.4	Web-based tool.....	15
2.5	Social Media Accounts.....	16
2.6	Social Media Management.....	18
2.7	Publication of Newsletters.....	19
2.7.1	Newsletter #1 (May 2023).....	20
2.7.2	Newsletter #2 (January 2024).....	21
2.7.3	Newsletter #3 (April 2025).....	23
2.7.4	Newsletter #4 (April 2025).....	24
2.8	Publication of Press Releases	25
3	Infographics.....	27
4	Videos.....	28
5	CLUSTER Poster	32
6	STAR4BBS Dissemination Activities.....	34
6.1	Events of communication and dissemination activities	34
6.2	Trainings.....	41
6.2.1	Training: “Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries”	41
6.2.2	Training: “Navigating the New EU Legislations to Address Greenwashing: How Standards and Research Projects Can Support the Bio-Based Industry”	43
6.2.3	Training: “Navigating the CSR Directive”	44
6.3	Establishment of Synergies and Networking with Other Projects.....	45
7	Conclusions.....	49

Index of Tables

Table 1: List of events for project promotion and impact maximization	34
---	----

Index of Figures

Figure 1: The Star4BBS Logo.....	12
Figure 2: STAR4BBS BMT infographic.....	12
Figure 3 Screenshots from website.....	13
Figure 4: Screenshots from Matomo analytics tool for 2025	15
Figure 5: The Star4BBS LinkedIn account.....	16
Figure 6: The Star4BBS X account.....	17
Figure 7: Example of Star4BBS LinkedIn account content.....	19
Figure 8: 1st Newsletter	20
Figure 9: 2nd Newsletter.....	22
Figure 10: 3rd Newsletter	23
Figure 11: 4th Newsletter	25
Figure 12: Project infographics.....	27
Figure 13: the BMT infographic.....	28
Figure 14: STAR4BBS project video	29
Figure 15: STAR4BBS WP1 video	29
Figure 16: STAR4BBS WP1 video	30
Figure 17: STAR4BBS WP2 video	30
Figure 18: STAR4BBS WP3 video	30
Figure 19: STAR4BBS WP4 video.....	31
Figure 20: STAR4BBS WP5 video.....	31
Figure 21: STAR4BBS WP6 video	31
Figure 22: STAR4BBS WP7 video	32
Figure 23: Cluster poster.....	33
Figure 24: Poster of training “Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries” organized by UNI.....	42
Figure 25: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop.....	42
Figure 26: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop.....	43
Figure 27: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop.....	45
Figure 28: collaboration with projects.....	46

Partners short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

Abbreviations

BMT	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSLs	Certification Schemes and Labels
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This report presents the Communication, Dissemination, and networking activities undertaken during the whole duration of the project.

The DEC strategy, led by APRE under Work Package 7, was designed to enhance project visibility, engage diverse stakeholders, and ensure the long-term sustainability of results. Communication efforts have included the creation of a strong project identity, development of visual materials, establishment and management of social media channels, publication of newsletters and press releases, and the redesign of the STAR4BBS website.

Dissemination actions have focused on knowledge sharing and policy support. Notable outputs include the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) featured on the STAR4BBS website, policy briefs, trainings, and extensive participation in international events and conferences. Synergies with sister projects and other EU-funded projects have also been cultivated, reinforcing the project's role as an important actor in the field of **voluntary sustainability certification schemes** to support a **sustainable circular bioeconomy**.

In conclusion, STAR4BBS Communication, Dissemination, and networking activities have laid a solid foundation for achieving its strategic objectives. The project has successfully mobilized stakeholders and initiated processes to ensure long-term result exploitation.

1 Introduction

STAR4BBS (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems) is a Horizon Europe-funded project launched in September 2022. It aims to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels in facilitating a successful transition toward a sustainable bio-based economy. This multidisciplinary and multi-actor initiative focuses on developing a fit-for-purpose monitoring system to assess the effectiveness, robustness, and traceability of existing international and EU-level certification schemes and labels related to biological feedstocks, bio-based materials, and products.

Through eight specific objectives, the project addresses issues ranging from mapping current schemes and trade flows to evaluating socio-environmental impacts and proposing practical recommendations. STAR4BBS engages a broad spectrum of stakeholders—including policymakers, academia, industry, and standard-setting organizations—to co-create outputs that ensure both scientific relevance and practical applicability.

STAR4BBS includes eight specific objectives (the infographic is available in **Error! Reference source not found.**):

1. gain a precise picture of existing international and EU SCS and labels both for biological feedstocks and biobased materials and products, as well existing monitoring systems;
2. gather specific global trade data and information on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products, differentiating between certified and uncertified flows;
3. explore the impact and contribution of existing SCS and labels to enabling sustainability and also the impact on the adoption of SCS and labels on market access and trade within bio-based systems, and to what extent sustainability SCS and labels are a catalyst or barrier;
4. identify relevant and feasible indicators, related metrics and minimum sustainability and traceability requirements for inclusion in the monitoring system;
5. develop a fit-for-purpose monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing SCS and labels in supporting achievement of sustainability targets and enabling transparent traceability in global trade flows;
6. assess the effectiveness and robustness of reviewed SCS and labels by applying the monitoring system;
7. evaluate overall costs and benefits from adopting the reviewed SCS and labels in selected value chains and performing a feasibility study on B2B labels best-performing from either environmental or social aspects;
8. maximize both the relevance and the uptake of the project findings and recommendations involving a broad range of stakeholders.

The project involved important stakeholders¹ (scheme owners, policy makers, and industry) in the design of the research and the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis, in order to ensure that the project achieves its goal.

1.1 Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Strategy

APRE, as WP7 leader, in close collaboration with the entire consortium, has developed the STAR4BBS Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D7.1) guiding the project's outreach activities throughout its duration. Coordinated by APRE under Work Package 7, the strategy defined clear objectives, target groups, tools, channels, and KPIs. It followed a four-phase structure: planning, implementation, monitoring, and sustainability. Communication efforts were tailored to seven distinct stakeholder groups, including standard-setting organizations, policy makers, and civil society, ensuring targeted and effective messaging.

The strategy was monitored and adjusted throughout the project, based on regular KPI assessments, enabling timely refinements and ensuring wide visibility and impact of STAR4BBS results.

This strategy addressed the following objectives:

- Target specific audiences that will benefit from the project's results and trigger them to adopt the STAR4BBS certification scheme model;
- Plan, design, implement, monitor, and evaluate a set of dissemination and communication activities;
- Increase the awareness about the project activities, results, and conclusions;
- Identify next steps for further development of certification schemes along the value chains and trades in the bio-based system for B2B communication tested during the project, facilitating their access to the market;
- Identify potential ways for ensuring the sustainability of the monitoring system beyond the duration of the project.

1.2 Communication Activities

Over the course of the project, STAR4BBS implemented a broad set of communication actions that successfully enhanced the project's visibility and stakeholder engagement.

The project website (<https://www.star4bbs.eu>), launched by M4, served as the main dissemination hub, offering access to project updates, results, and open-access deliverables. Six newsletters and four press releases were issued to provide targeted updates and increase outreach, that are publicly available on

¹ For more detailed information about the involvement of stakeholders, please refer to STA4RBSS, Deliverable 6.1 "STAR4BBS stakeholder map".

the project's [website](#). STAR4BBS maintained active [LinkedIn](#) and [X \(formerly Twitter\)](#) profiles, through which regular content—including news, event updates, videos, and infographics—was shared following a coordinated monthly editorial plan. STAR4BBS gathered over 530 followers across these platforms, and shared over 450 posts in three years.

STAR4BBS social media account highlighted the project's results and aimed at engaging the desired target audiences, encouraging them to actively participate in the events and workshops organized by the project and by the Cluster.

The project also produced a visual communication kit, complete with a logo and a recognizable brand identity, which served as a base for branded templates, flyers, and a project video. Moreover, APRE produced 5 infographics which translated in visual form important project concepts. The infographics have been made available to partners to use in presentations and events to support the dissemination and communication of project results.

Project partners actively participated in national and European events, webinars, and co-creation workshops, using these opportunities to promote STAR4BBS results. Communication efforts were tracked through a detailed monitoring system using KPIs, which demonstrated growing engagement and ensured alignment with strategic goals.

1.3 Dissemination Activities

Throughout its lifecycle, STAR4BBS implemented an extensive dissemination strategy led by APRE under Work Package 7, designed to maximize visibility, facilitate stakeholder engagement, and ensure uptake of project outputs. Activities included the continuous maintenance of a comprehensive project website and the publication of a well-designed communication kit—with logos, templates, and leaflets—available for download from the project portal. Regular press releases and newsletters highlighted milestones, workshops, and deliverable releases, while presentations at sector events (e.g., EUBCE workshop in Bologna 2023 and the "Standards and R&I Projects" workshop hosted by UNI in December 2023) showcased core findings and the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool to a European audience. Social media channels—LinkedIn and X—were active from month one, ensuring continuous outreach and promoting webinars, trainings, and recorded materials to foster transparency and community involvement. This mix of digital content, stakeholder workshops, and event engagement ensured that STAR4BBS results were widely disseminated and primed for replication.

2 STAR4BBS Communication Activities

The present chapter summarizes the Communication activities performed within the STAR4BBS Strategy implementation.

All STAR4BBS communication activities have been based on the logo and visual identity toolkit developed by APRE at the beginning of the project (M4) to establish a recognizable and engaging project image.

In the following paragraphs, a detailed report of the activities performed through the various project's tools and channels will be presented. The activities have been developed and managed using the Strategy as a baseline to implement its core vision and mission.

The communication activities carried out so far have been a collaborative effort between APRE, the WP8 leader, and the whole consortium. APRE is tasked to prepare content for communication materials and for the project's social media accounts. Partners are asked to share relevant news and events, and to share the project's official content as much as possible within their networks.

Below are the specific activities undertaken during the aforementioned period, highlighting milestones, progress, and preliminary outcomes.

2.1 Development of Visual Communication Materials

A complete visual communication toolkit was developed to ensure brand consistency across all communication channels. The toolkit included the graphic elements that make the project recognizable and were applied to social media accounts and the website, communication and dissemination materials (e.g. flyers and roll up), and different templates for deliverables and presentations:

- A project logo (original, monochrome, vertical versions) (see Figure 1)
- Brand identity guide,
- Word (for deliverable and agenda) and PowerPoint presentation templates,
- Flyers (translated in 6 languages), virtual background, and roll-up ,
- 5 Infographics (see Figure 2, as an example).

Figure 1 depicts the STAR4BBS Logo.

Figure 1: The Star4BBS Logo

Figure 2 depicts the STAR4BBS BMT infographics.

Figure 2: STAR4BBS BMT infographic

These materials are actively used at events, conferences, and in stakeholder communication.

2.2 WEBSITE

The STAR4BBS website (<https://star4bbs.eu/>) served as the central hub for project communication and dissemination, offering structured and accessible information for all stakeholder groups.

The project's website has been online since Month 4, in the English version. Moreover, the projects' "Mission" section has been translated into all consortium languages to improve accessibility and inclusion. The translated pages have been available through pop-up pages since April 2024 (M19).

In Figure 3 below, a screenshot from the website.

Figure 3 Screenshots from website

The website has been developed on WordPress by MLPStudio, that built the custom theme for the pages, based on the previously created visual identity. This was implemented coherently, considering also UI (User Interface) parameters that allow a smooth and easy navigation of the website.

The website features a clear and user-friendly layout, organized into several key sections.

The **Home page** introduces the project's mission (translatable in the Consortium languages) objectives and latest updates, and showcases the project's promotional video.

The **About** section provides detailed information on the project's background, consortium partners, and specific goals. It also gives the access to the **Results** section that hosted public deliverables, infographics, and policy briefs, ensuring transparency and knowledge sharing. Finally, the Advisory Board section with a short description of this project body and the members.

A dedicated **Workflow** area outlines the structure and tasks of each WP, highlighting key outputs.

The **News & Events** area shares updates on project milestones, participation in conferences, and upcoming activities.

Additionally, a Join Our Community page enables visitors to subscribe to newsletters and engage with the project, while respecting GDPR compliance.

The site also includes direct access to STAR4BBS's social media channels. Overall, the website effectively supported the project's outreach and stakeholder engagement goals.

Between its kickoff in September 2022 and the project's close, the **STAR4BBS "News & Events"** section served as a dynamic chronicle of milestones, workshops, external engagements, publications, and key outputs. Early announcements included the project's launch, attendance at Projects2Projects and the European Bioplastic Conference, and stakeholder consultation workshops on sustainability policy targets. Throughout 2023 and 2024, a steady stream of activity was documented: the hybrid Sustainability Certification Conference at EUBCE, co-creation workshops with the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, field days, and events like "Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries". In early 2025, STAR4BBS shared published peer-reviewed articles and key outputs, including a "Reporting on Biogenic Feedstocks and Bio-Based Products" report.

The site also hosted detailed accounts and downloadable recordings of major webinars and trainings held in March and April 2025—on the EU Green Claims Directive, CSR Directive implementation, and combating greenwashing. Additionally, the final BIOBASEDCERT cluster conference, held in May 2025 at the European Commission DG RTD, showcased the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool and policy recommendations.

2.3 WEBSITE metrics

A monitoring software, Matomo, was also installed starting from September 2023, in order to keep track of STAR4BBS' progress towards the KPIs set by D7.1 for website activities. Matomo was used instead of Google Analytics 4, as this software is GDPR compliant and better protects privacy of users. Using Matomo (see Figure 4), it is possible to extract data relevant to understand STAR4BBS' website growth:

- Number of visits: 7000 visits (KPI: 5.000 in 3 years);
- Average visit duration: 1min30sec (KPI: 75% of visitors stays more than one minute);
- Website content shared by external users on Social Networks: 200 outlinks (KPI: 200 in 3 years).

Some KPIs were revised during the first RP; the main reason is that the topic is very specific to have such a large number of followers. It is highlighted that STAR4BBS' number of followers is in line with the numbers reached so far from the sister projects.

Figure 4 shows the Matomo analytics management panel interface.

Figure 4: Screenshots from Matomo analytics tool for 2025

2.4 Web-based tool

As part of its commitment to maximizing the practical applicability of BIOBASEDCERT cluster results, an interactive web-based self-assessment tool was designed to support stakeholders in evaluating the robustness and effectiveness of their sustainability certification schemes. The tool will be hosted in a specific webpage on the STAR4BBS website. Users will be able to create an account to undertake the benchmarking exercise, save progress, and download results in both PDF and CSL form. APRE is committed to hosting this service on the website for 5 years after the end of the STAR4BBS project's funding period.

The web-based version of the tool is based on the Excel-based BMT, developed during the sister projects implementation and conceptualized as an online system, where users respond to a predefined set of questions. The answers are benchmarked against reference values contained in the backend database, with the results visualized through spider diagrams, tabular and other formats to highlight strengths, weaknesses, and overall performance across key dimensions. Developed in collaboration with a dedicated web developer, the tool features a React/Vite-based frontend supported by a custom REST API for data storage and user interaction. Although initially designed for anonymous use without user registration, the architecture allowed for future scalability,

including the option to implement user accounts, historical result tracking, and multilingual support.

The tool was integrated into a dedicated section of the STAR4BBS website, offering a practical and user-friendly interface for stakeholders to engage directly with the project’s assessment framework and better understand the performance of their schemes.

The tool will be available for use from July 2025 and maintained for the next 5 years (up to 2030).

2.5 Social Media Accounts

APRE has been consistently communicating and disseminating the project activities on the project’s social media. STAR4BBS has a LinkedIn account and an X/Twitter account, both under the name: @STAR4BBS, to ensure easy identification and accessibility, to be reached by relevant target groups.

Figure 5, a screenshot of the LinkedIn account shows its features.

Figure 5: The Star4BBS LinkedIn account

These platforms now serve as primary communication tools for stakeholder engagement and public outreach.

Below, Figure 6 is a screenshot of the STAR4BBS’s X account.

Figure 6: The Star4BBS X account

For its social media strategy, STAR4BBS uses LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) (see Figure 5 and Figure 6) as its channels to ensure targeted outreach and engagement. LinkedIn was selected for its professional audience, enabling direct interaction with key stakeholders such as certification bodies, researchers, policy makers, and industry actors. It serves as an effective platform for sharing project updates, results, and event invitations within relevant professional networks. X was chosen to increase visibility among a broader audience, including other EU-funded projects, NGOs, and the general public, and to foster informal interactions and real-time dissemination of news and achievements. The combination of these platforms allowed the project to balance professional credibility with wider reach, while tracking engagement through platform-specific analytics to inform content strategy and optimize communication efforts.

2.6 Social Media Management

Ongoing management of the STAR4BBS social media accounts has been maintained throughout this period by APRE. A content calendar - implemented to coordinate posts, and continuous communication with the Coordination Team and the Partners - ensured that the content shared is relevant and targeted to the project's audience.

The content shared so far on the different social media platforms is as follows:

- **LinkedIn:** ~ 200 posts (updates, event coverage, partner highlights).
- **X (formerly Twitter):** ~200 tweets (real-time engagement during events, sharing of partner presentations, updates);

Analytics indicate a steady increase in follower growth, engagement rates, and link clicks, demonstrating the effectiveness of these outreach channels.

N. 189 original content posts have been published:

- on LinkedIn, the posts received an average of 200 views each, click-through rate on average 2.83%, and an average engagement rate of 9.90%;
- on X/Twitter the posts received an average of 60 views, and around an average of 10.1% interactions per post each month;
- The YouTube channel has 11 subscribers, and 12 videos have been uploaded. The average views are 15 per video.

The project has reached a total of 535 followers, 424 from LinkedIn and 111 from X/Twitter. The KPI foreseen in D7.1 for Social Media accounts is to gather at least 2000 followers in the three years of the project. However, given the sectoral and specialized topic treated by the project, an adjustment is necessary. APRE believes that, considering the outputs and insights obtained from the implementation of communication and dissemination activities, reaching 1000 followers in 3 years is a satisfactory achievement in showcasing STAR4BBS' results.

Figure 7 is added below as an example of the content shared on the project's social media account, showing one of the latest posts of the Consortium activities.

Figure 7: Example of Star4BBS LinkedIn account content

2.7 Publication of Newsletters

A total of 5 project newsletters will be developed and distributed to the project’s subscribers; 4 of them have been already issued, the next will be delivered in July, and the final issue will be shared for the project’s end.

Each newsletter was disseminated via email to all stakeholder registered via our “join our Community” website and published on the STAR4BBS website, contributing to accessibility to information.

2.7.1 Newsletter #1 (May 2023)

star4bbs.eu_1st Newsletter

The first issue was released in May 2023, it is available on the project’s website for download and is outlined as follows (see Figure 8):

1. Introduction by the coordinator Dr. Luana Ladu
2. STAR4BBS in a nutshell: short presentation of the project, on
3. STAR4BBS activities, partners, WPs/outputs. Description of the partners
4. Project clustering referencing the websites of the two sister projects.
5. Presentation of the Advisory board
6. Latest news and announcements
7. Save the date: reminder for future activities and events related to STAR4BBS topics (as of 05/30/2023)
8. Follow us: Useful links to follow project activities (social media and website)

Figure 8 wants to give an example of the project’s brand identity applied to the newsletters, in particular, it shows the initial pages of the 1st issue.

Figure 8: 1st Newsletter

Newsletter #1, the inaugural edition, introduced STAR4BBS to its target audience and outlined the initial roadmap for achieving its objectives.

Project Inception: The issue opened with a welcome message from the project coordinators, officially announcing the launch of STAR4BBS and its ambition to enhance the sustainability of bio-based systems through rigorous monitoring

and assessment tools. It included a summary of the consortium members, their areas of expertise, and the project timeline extending to 2025.

Stakeholder Engagement: This edition spotlighted plans for the first stakeholder brainstorming sessions to be held in Summer 2023. It invited certification bodies, industry associations, researchers, and policy experts to participate in these consultations designed to inform the structure of the monitoring system and highlight relevant sustainability dimensions across feedstock and products.

Communication Launch: Newsletter #1 also announced STAR4BBS's digital presence, unveiling the project website, LinkedIn page, and Twitter (X) profile. It encouraged subscribing to newsletters, following social media channels, and registering for upcoming events to stay informed about project milestones and outputs.

Next Steps: Finally, the newsletter outlined short-term plans: conducting benchmarking of existing certification schemes and labels, developing the first set of sustainability and operability indicators, and preparing for the first co-creation workshop. It concluded with a call to engage early and ensure the project's tools would meet stakeholder needs.

2.7.2 Newsletter #2 (January 2024)

star4bbs.eu_2nd Newsletter

Newsletter #2 marked a pivotal moment in STAR4BBS's journey, transitioning from foundation and planning to broader stakeholder engagement and preliminary results dissemination. The second issue of the newsletters (see Figure 9) was released in January 2024, and subsequently uploaded on the project website (with a download option), and is outlined as follows:

1. One year of STAR4BBS: a look back on the first year of the project
2. Recap of work done
 - a. Methodology: STAR4BBS method of work
 - b. UniTelma Sapienza updates
 - c. Technische Universität Berlin updates
 - d. Nova Institute updates
 - e. ISEAL updates
3. Looking Forward: next steps of the project
4. Latest News and past events
5. Follow Us: useful links to project's social media and website

In Figure 9 the first pages of the 2nd newsletter:

Figure 9: 2nd Newsletter

Project Progress Overview: This edition recapped the main achievements of the first half of the project, including the completion of mapping of existing CSLs impact, the analysis of biomass trade flows, and the review of existing monitoring systems. It emphasized the consortium's efforts in collecting data from various feedstock value chains and synthesizing stakeholder feedback aligned with WP3 and WP4 objectives.

Updates from Partners: UnitelmaSapienza, TU Berlin, NOVA, and ISEAL shared with readers a summary of their activities to update them on their progress. UnitelmaSapienza wrote about their comprehensive analysis of the existing international and EU SCS and labels for feedstock and bio-based materials and products, which showed a growing number of schemes and labels applicable to bio-based value chains.

TU Berlin commented on their analysis of existing monitoring tools to assess and compare SCS, underlining that key recommendations stemming from this create a tool for promoting sustainability in the bio-based economy and for driving responsible practices in the bio-based products supply chain.

NOVA suggested that the systematic literature review of EU sustainability policies and targets relevant for the SCS and labels indicates the existence of a large number of sustainability targets in recent policies, but these are rather general or non-binding.

Finally, ISEAL, together with Evidensia, provided an overview of the available evidence of SCS and labels' impacts on Greenhouse Gas reducing emissions. Shortly, results showed that the academic evidence base is very limited and dominated by research on the production of feedstocks.

Stakeholder Workshops & Events: The newsletter highlighted two major co-creation workshops, where policy makers, NGOs, industry representatives, and scheme owners collaboratively validated the first draft of the monitoring system and its structure. It summarized key takeaways, such as the need to balance rigor and user-friendliness, and to ensure compatibility with existing certification systems.

2.7.3 Newsletter #3 (April 2025)

star4bbs.eu_3rd Newsletter

The third issue of the newsletters (see Figure 10) was released in April 2025. Newsletter #3 offered readers an overview of the latest scientific and policy-oriented outputs from STAR4BBS, reflecting the project's transition from implementation to results dissemination.

Figure 10 shows the first page of the 3rd newsletter.

Figure 10: 3rd Newsletter

Publications: The newsletter featured a spotlight on to D1.3 (“Report on impact and contribution of existing SCS and B2B Labels”) and D2.2 (“Report on matching biogenic flows with certification systems”), in addition to BIOBASEDCERT Cluster deliverables D7.4 (“Mid-term Clustering Report”) and D7.5. (“Mid-term Policy Brief “). The 3rd issue also contained direct links to all deliverables available on the STAR4BBS website for download: D2.1 (“Concept and methodology for collecting volumes of biogenic feedstock”), D3.2 (“Report on additional indicators of monitoring system”), D6.1 (“STAR4BBS stakeholder map”), D7.3 (“Action Plan for joint activities with other projects funded under

the ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 topic"), D8.1 ("Report on Project Management"), D8.2 ("Initial Data Management Plan"), and D8.3 ("Ethical Issues Report").

Progress on Activities: This section highlighted the progress made by the STAR4BBS Consortium for data collection and analysis of production volumes and trade flows for selected bio-based feedstocks and products and to define a methodology to match these flows with certification schemes. The paragraph also underlined the finalization of the selection process of test cases for the cost-benefit analysis. Finally, the successful submission of D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 was announced. These documents relate to the outline of key environmental, economic, circularity, and social indicators, with both Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and non-LCA perspectives.

Upcoming activities: the newsletter invited the lectors to join the upcoming 6th STAR4BBS Co-Creation Workshop (online on the 11th of November). The output of the workshop is described in details in D6.2, that can be found on Zenodo and on the project website as soon as it is approved.

Latest activities: this issue described the General Assembly of the STAR4BBS consortium, on September 19-20 in Athens. In addition to that the newsletter illustrated the output from the BIOBASEDCERT cluster event hold at EUBCE 2024, titled "Monitoring Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Products." The output of the workshop is described in detail in D6.2, that can be found on Zenodo and on the project website as soon as it is approved.

2.7.4 Newsletter #4 (April 2025)

[star4bbs.eu_4th newsletter](#)

Newsletter #4 (Figure 11) celebrated the collaborative achievements of STAR4BBS as it neared its conclusion, with a strong emphasis on stakeholder engagement, cross-project cooperation, and co-creation activities.

Strategic Collaborations: The newsletter opened with a reflection on the role of multi-stakeholder collaboration, featuring a quote from Ilaria Bientinesi (APRE): "Stakeholder collaboration can spark innovation, solve problems, and build on mutual knowledge." It detailed how STAR4BBS worked within the sister projects HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to form the BIOBASEDCERT cluster and co-develop the shared BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), co-design policy recommendations, and conduct joint capacity-building initiatives.

Ecosystex Engagement: STAR4BBS's role in broader networks such as ECOSYSTEEX was also highlighted. It partnered with other Horizon Europe projects, including SUSTRACK, BioReCer, and 3-CO, and co-organized events

such as a CSR-focused webinar with ENGAGE4BIO, reinforcing the project’s contribution to the larger European bioeconomy policy discourse.

Timeline of Co-Creation Workshops: A detailed timeline summarized the co-creation activities held between January 2023 and December 2024. These are described in detail in D6.2, that can be found on Zenodo and on the project website as soon as it is approved:

- Stakeholder consultations on prioritizing sustainability targets (January 2023, online),
- Workshops validating the draft monitoring framework (May 2023, online)
- Sustainability certification of bio-based products (June 2023, Bologna, Italy)
- Certified trade in bio-based value chains (June 2024, Cologne, Germany).

Final Event Invitation: The newsletter concluded with an invitation to the **BIOBASEDCERT final conference**, scheduled for May 13–14, 2025, in Brussels. The event featured live demonstrations of the Monitoring Tool, interactive stakeholder panels, and sessions aimed at utilizing STAR4BBS findings as a contribution to shaping the future of the EU Bioeconomy policy framework.

Figure 11 is a screenshot of how the 4th newsletter was developed.

Figure 11: 4th Newsletter

2.8 Publication of Press Releases

STAR4BBS project issued its first EU press release explaining the importance of reliable, harmonised certification systems for ensuring transparency and credibility in sustainability claims across bio-based value chains. It detailed the project's efforts to map and assess existing schemes, collect international trade and biomass data, and engage with stakeholders. The press release also announced STAR4BBS' collaboration with two sister projects—HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED—in developing a Joint Monitoring System (later named BMT) and carrying out joint dissemination actions via the Horizon Results Booster. It concluded by reaffirming the need for harmonised metrics and robust certification frameworks to meet EU sustainability goals.

It was published on EUBIONET website: <https://eubionet.eu/star4bbs-first-eu-press-release-october-2023/>

The second press release was dedicated to the two high-level online trainings held in March 2025. The sessions focused on critical topics for the bio-based sector: addressing greenwashing through credible standards and complying with the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). The press release helped amplify visibility of the events, encouraged stakeholder engagement, and provided access to recordings and materials to support ongoing capacity-building efforts across the sector.

It was published on EUBIONET website [STAR4BBS Empowers Bio-Based Industry Through Two High-Caliber April Trainings on Greenwashing & CSRD Compliance – The European Bioeconomy Network](#)

A third publication was released after the draft of the “Final Policy Brief of the BIOBASEDCERT Project Cluster”, that can be found on Zenodo and on the project website as soon as it will be approved. The press release highlighted the BIOBASEDCERT Final Policy Brief findings and recommendations, including critical gaps in EU bioeconomy sustainability certification, the launch of the innovative BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), and seven urgent policy recommendations addressing policy fragmentation, trade monitoring, and certification standardization. The press release emphasized the cluster's development of the first harmonized system to assess certification scheme robustness and effectiveness, while calling for European Commission adoption of the BMT to drive transparency and provide direction for bio-based markets. The communication targeted policymakers, industry stakeholders, and media outlets to disseminate research findings and promote policy action for sustainable bioeconomy development.

It was published on EUBIONET website [EU Bioeconomy Needs Urgent Policy Action to Address Sustainability Certification Gaps – The European Bioeconomy Network](#)

The fourth press release was dedicated to the BIOBASEDCERT Final Conference (13 May 2025, Brussels) to highlight key outcomes and policy insights. The release focused on the role of voluntary sustainability certification

in supporting the EU’s circular bioeconomy transition, showcasing the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), key findings from expert discussions, and the cluster’s joint policy recommendations. It was disseminated through project channels and stakeholder networks to maximise outreach and visibility.

<https://eubionet.eu/biobasedcert-final-conference/>

The fifth -and final- press release will be published to announce the end of the project in September 2025, highlighting the project’s achievements in the past 3 years.

3 Infographics

The infographics developed for the STAR4BBS project serve as a clear and engaging visual communication tool to outline the project's core objectives. Each step, from the analysis of existing Certification and Sustainability Labels (CSLs) to the formulation of policy recommendations, is visually represented to enhance stakeholder understanding and engagement. These communication activities aim to make complex processes more accessible to diverse audiences—including policymakers, researchers, and industry stakeholders—by using intuitive icons, concise language, and a logical flow. This approach not only increases visibility and transparency of the project goals but also fosters better stakeholder involvement and support throughout the project lifecycle.

In Figure 12, an example of the first infographic that was chosen to be developed by APRE and TUB: the 8 objectives of the STAR4BBS project. In Figure 13, the infographic created to make more accessible and visually engaging the BMT Tool and its features.

Figure 12: Project infographics.

Figure 13: the BMT infographic.

4 Videos

At M22, APRE in collaboration with TUB, developed and published a short video presenting the key aims and goals of the STAR4BBS project. The video was published on YouTube and was disseminated on the project's social media platform. It currently holds more than 50 views, and it is also featured on the project's website homepage.

In Figure 14, a still image from the video showing consumers consulting a label.

Figure 14: STAR4BBS project video

Moreover, APRE conducted 8 short interviews with WP leaders, who explained their work in the STAR4BBS project and to easily explain benefits of the projects' results for the targeted audience. All videos have been published on YouTube and on the project's social media channel. [STAR4BBS - YouTube](#). The links are provided below, together with screenshots extracted from the video interviews, depicted from Figure 15 to Figure 22.

[Dr. Luana Ladu introduces STAR4BBS project](#)

Figure 15: STAR4BBS WP1 video

[STAR4BBS- Work Package 1, UNITELMA insights](#)

Figure 16: STAR4BBS WP1 video

[STAR4BBS- Work Package 2, Nova Institute insights](#)

Figure 17: STAR4BBS WP2 video

[STAR4BBS- Work Package 3 insights, University of Santiago de Compstela](#)

Figure 18: STAR4BBS WP3 video

[STAR4BBS- Work Package 4 Insights, Technische Universität Berlin \(TUB\)](#)

Figure 19: STAR4BBS WP4 video

[Work Package 5 insights, Agricultural University of Athens](#)

Figure 20: STAR4BBS WP5 video

[Work Package 6 insights, Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca in Europa \(APRE\)](#)

Work Package 6 insights, Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca in Europa (APRE)

Figure 21: STAR4BBS WP6 video

Work Package 7 Insights,
Agenzia per la Promozione
della Ricerca in Europa

Work Package 7 Insights, Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca in Europa

Figure 22: STAR4BBS WP7 video

The video interviews allowed Work Package leaders to explain their activities in the project, giving a clear overview of the structure and methodology guiding the work. Each Work Package leader promoted the Work Package results and contributed in disseminating STAR4BBS.

5 CLUSTER Poster

APRE worked in collaboration with ICONS, who developed the visual material of the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster, to use the visual identity further and to translate complex project research into engaging materials for workshops or conferences, like the poster that can be seen in Figure 23.

BIOBASEDCERT

Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems

BIOBASEDCERT Cluster is a group of three EU-funded projects (2022-2025), developing and testing the **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System (BMS)** to assess the **effectiveness and robustness of international and EU sustainability certification schemes and labels**, applicable to bio-based systems.

The **BIOBASEDCERT Cluster** provides:

- BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System (BMS);
- Assessment of certification schemes and labels;
- Transparent data on bio-based value chains, including analysis of trade flows;
- Costs and benefits assessment, including feasibility study;
- Stakeholder recommendations.

 sustcert4biobased.eu

Several international and EU sustainability standards have been developed and are applied for biological feedstock and biobased products through voluntary certification schemes and labels. They serve as powerful instruments to assess the sustainability of bio-based products.

HARMONITOR

 harmonitor.eu

However, their rapid proliferation led to questioning their effectiveness and robustness. To ensure that the transition to circular biobased systems occurs sustainably, it is essential to evaluate the performance of these tools.

 star4bbs.eu

This is where BIOBASEDCERT Cluster comes into play!

This poster has been produced by APPE in the context of the Horizon Results Booster services delivered by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (GA n.101099785), HARMONITOR (GA n.101366133), and STAR4BBS (GA n.101394588). This product does not reflect the views of the European Commission.

Let's advance the bio-based economy together

Figure 23: Cluster poster.

6 STAR4BBS Dissemination Activities

This chapter presents a detailed review of the STAR4BBS project efforts for dissemination, highlighting efforts as part of the project's commitment to impactful stakeholder engagement and strategic knowledge sharing.

These activities have been carefully aligned with the project's Communication and Dissemination Strategy, carrying out its objectives, involving the defined target audiences, and utilizing the appropriate channels to maximize the uptake and long-term value of STAR4BBS results.

Each dissemination action contributed to meeting the project's expectations in terms of visibility and awareness, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge sharing.

6.1 Events of communication and dissemination activities

The Consortium has been consistently engaged in participating in events and conferences throughout these 36 months of implementation. In particular, partners have disseminated not only the project objectives within their networks, but also actively looking for relevant events to highlight STAR4BBS impact in the field.

Below is a list of national and international events and conferences where Partners have promoted the project and maximized its impact, available in **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Table 1: List of events for project promotion and impact maximization

Date	Activity Name	Main output	Target audience Reached	Type
26/09/2022	Horizon Europe STAR4BBS project kicks off	Project kick-off announcement	Project partners, bio-economy community	Comm
05/10/2022	Participation in Projects2projects event (by EuBioNet)	Introducing the start of STAR4BSS (aim+objectives), finding and setup future collaborations between other European bioeconomy projects EU-funded	Research communities, Industry, business partners, EU Institutions,	Diss

05/10/2022	EUBioNet workshop		Participation at EUBioNet workshop, "Maximise the exploitation of lessons learnt and heritage of Horizon2020 bioeconomy projects in communication, education, and stakeholders engagement to effectively kick off the newly funded Horizon Europe ones.	Research communities	Comm
11/10/2022	The Green transition between training, innovation		Presentation of STAR4BBS project at the conferences	Research communities	Diss
11/10/2022	Festival dello Sviluppo Sostenibile	dello	Participation to the Festival dello Sviluppo sostenibile where the project was presented	Research communities	Comm
03/11/2022	Glaukos Workshop		Participation at BioPlastics Europe-Insights from 10 Horizon Project: EU Plastics for bio-based and biodegradable plastics	Research communities	Comm
06/12/2022	European Bioplastic Conferences 2023		Project Poster presentation by TUB	Industry, business partners	Diss

15/12/2022	Presentation at European Bioplastic conference	Project awareness presentation	Researchers, industry stakeholders	Diss
14/02/2023	SUSTRACK Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop	Project presented at SUSTRACK 1st Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring	Research communities	Comm
16/03/2023	Focus Area day BAM	STAR4BBS was presented at the focus area day of the thematic field "environment", an internal event of BAM.	Research communities	Comm
21/03/2023	Environmental field day by BAM	Field insights, stakeholder engagement	Industry & policy actors	Comm
25/03/2023	First stakeholder consultation workshop	Prioritisation of sustainability policy targets	Stakeholders (academia, industry, policy)	Diss
05/04/2023	Green Claims Directive launch	Awareness of EU initiative to tackle greenwashing	Certification bodies, bio-based industry	Diss
27/04/2023	Int. Research workshop on Quality Infrastructure	Presentation of the project by a speech incl. Powerpoint-presentation by Dr. Ladu Luana.	Research communities	Diss
27/04/2023	PTB-QI Research workshop	Project presented at PTB-QI Research workshop on the	Research communities	Comm

		27th of April 2023.		
12/05/2023	Workshop at EUBCE (Bologna)	Presentations + roundtable on CSLs and monitoring tool	Conference participants, stakeholders	Diss
4-9/06/2023	11th WORLD CONGRESS OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING (WCCE11)	Presentation of the project titled: "Biorefinery development using crude renewable resources and the contribution of certification"	Research communities	Diss
07/06/2023	Joint workshop on sustainability certification	Preliminary results and stakeholder roundtable discussion	Bio-based project community	Diss
07/06/2023	EUBCE 2023 European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	Side Event on sustainability certification for bio-based products organized with sister projects	Research communities	Diss
07/06/2023	EUBCE 2023 European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	Project presentation at EUBCE - European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	Research communities	Comm
12/06/2023	Conference on sustainability certification of bio-based products	Shared knowledge on CSLs	Academia, industry	Diss
17/06/2023	Long Night of the Sciences	Poster and information about the	Other	Diss

		project in a stand		
29/09/2023	Researchers Night	Poster and information about the project in a stand	Other	Diss
28-29/09/2023	International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy (IFIB 2023)	STAR4BBS Consortium to organize a side event on “How to measure robustness and effectiveness of sustainability certification systems for the bio-based industry”. In addition, partners participated at the two-day conference, contributing with their poster abstracts, presentations and by participating at the round tables. IFIB brought together many bioeconomy stakeholders from around the world, who gathered to discuss and present the latest updates in the field. The STAR4BBS project coordinator Dr.	Research communities	Comm

		Luana Ladu (TUB) illustrated the efforts performed towards the evaluation of the robustness and effectiveness of sustainability certification systems for the bio-based industry.		
20-22/10/2023	Makers Faire 2023	Distribution of promotional materials Poster and information about the project in a stand	Citizens	Comm
24/10/2023	Projects2Projects workshop	Exchange among related Horizon Europe projects	Project peers	Diss
06/11/2023	RSB Collaborative Sustainable Initiative	Project presentation	Research communities	Diss
14/12/2023	Standards and R&I Projects for BioBased Industries	Project presented exploitation of standardization results at online event "Standards and R&I Projects for BioBased Industries" organized by UNI	Research communities	Comm
10-12/01/2024	GEOINNO 2024	Paper presentation: How to Measure the Robustness and	Research communities	Diss

		Effectiveness of Certification Schemes and Labels in Ensuring the Sustainability of Bio-based Products		
24-28/07/2023	CILCA 2023	Presentation of WP3 Preliminary results	Research communities	Diss
5-9/06/2023	EUBCE – European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	Project workshop Event "Sustainability certification of bio-based products Conference" organized with sister projects	Research communities	Comm
12/02/2025	Peer-reviewed article published	Article on the Green Claims Directive	Academia, policy researchers	Diss
28/02/2025	Training webinar on CSRD	Insights into CSRD compliance in bio-based reporting	Bio-based industry, SMEs, policy experts	Diss
25 Mar 2025	Online training: "Addressing greenwashing"	Recording, slides, EU leg committee insights	Certification bodies, industry, standards-setters	Diss
13-14/05/2025	BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference	Final conference outcomes, policy recommendations, cluster monitoring tool launch	EU policy-makers, R&I community	Diss

6.2 Trainings

The STAR4BBS project organised several training sessions to disseminate project results. APRE supported UNI with the creation of engaging materials to use and to promote events among the target audience. TUB, USC and the projects members of the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster actively participated in the training identifying relevant topics, providing and leading panels, and sending out invitations within their networks.

6.2.1 Training: “Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries”

Workshop on “Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries” organized by UNI (Decemebr 14, 2023) - STAR4BBS

The first open training on “**Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries**” (see Figure 24) was performed on **December 14 2023** and organized by UNI, with the support of APRE and TUB. The dissemination of the event has leveraged on the Framework Agreement UNI has with the system of the Italian Chamber of Commerce, and this has facilitated a good participation of companies. The training aimed to shed light on the standardization world: how it works, which are the main actors, what is the link with certification. It also highlighted how organizations can transform R&I results into a fast-track standardization document, the CEN Workshop Agreement – CWA. It has also involved other two Horizon projects, Bioradar and Biorecer, to start exploring eventual standardization outcomes, while disseminating their objectives and intermediate results to companies, research institutions and standardization experts.

The training is considered as a great success and an important opportunity to interact with stakeholders, collect feedback, and share the results of the project activities. In total, **75 participants** registered to the event, among which: research centers and universities; standardization and certification actors; regional chamber of commerce; national and international companies and SMEs.

Figure 24 below depicts the poster created to promote the event on social media and within various networks, while Figure 25 provides a still image from the implementation of the event.

Figure 24: Poster of training “Standards and R&I Projects for Bio-Based Industries” organized by UNI.

Figure 25: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop.

The training was recorded and disseminated, along with the materials, on the websites of 3 projects (BIORECER; BIORADAR; STAR4BBS) (Figure 15).

6.2.2 Training: “Navigating the New EU Legislations to Address Greenwashing: How Standards and Research Projects Can Support the Bio-Based Industry”

<https://star4bbs.eu/2025/04/04/recording-and-slides-of-the-25th-of-march-2025-on-addressing-greenwashing/>

On March 25, 2025, STAR4BBS—together with SUSTCERT4BIOBASED—hosted an intensive two-hour online training session titled “Navigating the New EU Legislations to Address Greenwashing: How Standards and Research Projects Can Support the Bio-Based Industry”. The event offered a sharp focus on the latest EU regulatory measures targeting misleading environmental claims, including the Green Claims Directive, and provided actionable insights on how certification schemes and monitoring frameworks such as the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) can reinforce credibility and transparency in the bio-based sector. Participants benefited from presentations by experts including Elena Mocchio, Gustavo De Feo, Margaux Le Gallou, and representatives from the BMT team, all of which were recorded and made available alongside their slides for ongoing reference.

In Figure 26 below, a screenshot of the training workshop.

Figure 26: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop.

The event gathered 59 registered participants (44 attending participants) from across Europe with a focus on how research and standards can help the bio-based industry combat greenwashing.

Key presentations included insights into EU legislation by Margaux Le Gallou (ECOS), innovative analytical methods for bio-based materials by Gustavo Adrián Defeo (CEN TC289), and the cluster's collective efforts on sustainability certification from TU Berlin and ECOS representatives.

The session featured dynamic Q&A session and concluded with a rich panel discussion, underscoring the need for transparent, evidence-based sustainability claims. The high level of engagement highlighted the relevance of the topic and the importance of continued collaboration among standardization bodies, research projects, and industry stakeholders.

The recording of the training is available on STAR4BBS' YouTube account, while the presenters' slides are published on the project's website.

6.2.3 Training: "Navigating the CSR Directive"

<https://star4bbs.eu/2025/04/04/recording-and-slides-of-the-14th-of-march-training-on-navigating-the-csr-directive/>

On March 14, 2025, STAR4BBS hosted a comprehensive online training titled **"Navigating the CSR Directive: Leveraging Voluntary Sustainability Standards and Research to Strengthen Bio-Based Industry Reporting"**, designed to help stakeholders understand and implement the new Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive. The session featured expert presentations that clarified key reporting requirements, guidance for certifiers and producers on aligning with EU sustainability frameworks, and use-case demonstrations of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool to support compliance. Participants received the full recording and slide deck, enabling ongoing reference and promoting consistent adoption of the directive's best practices across the bio-based supply chain. A screenshot from the live event can be seen in Figure 27 below.

Figure 27: Recorded video screenshot of the training workshop

The training session was able to reach 52 registered participants (35 attending), between professionals from across sectors.

Presentations covered the key elements of the CSRD, the role of research in facilitating its implementation, and how life-cycle thinking supports sustainable innovation. Speakers included experts from CISE, UNI, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, and Metropolia.

The session concluded with a discussion moderated by Luana Ladu (TU Berlin), where participants exchanged insights on aligning sustainability reporting with EU taxonomy and industry needs. The event was well-received, reflecting growing interest in harmonizing reporting practices through research and voluntary standards.

The recording of the training is available on STAR4BBS' YouTube account, while the presenters' slides are published on the project's website.

6.3 Establishment of Synergies and Networking with Other Projects

STAR4BBS liaises with other European funded projects on similar topics, defined collaborations, exchanged information and expertise, cross-fertilize and increase the collective impacts of the projects in the field of **Bioeconomy, Sustainable certification schemes, Labels, Monitoring systems**.

Those projects were invited and cooperated in the cluster's Final Conference and in the trainings.

The website section showcasing STAR4BBS synergies can be seen in Figure 28.

Figure 28: collaboration with projects

STAR4BBS is a Member Project of ECOSYSTEMX, a European network of projects joining forces to build a community of practice and strengthen cooperation in the field of textile sustainability and circularity.

As mentioned before, STAR4BBS also established a formal cluster with two sister projects (HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED) to form the cluster under the name BIOBASEDCERT - “Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems”. To ensure that the three projects work together effectively, a coordinated and collaborative approach was established very early (end of 2022 / starting of 2023). A clear action plan was defined with several joint cooperation activities that the projects would undertake to align their goals, avoid duplication of efforts, and maximize their impact. The cluster drafted together several deliverables, (D4.2-BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT); D7.3-Action Plan for joint activities with other projects funded under the ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 topic²; D7.4-Mid-term clustering report for HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07³; D7.5-First Policy Brief⁴; D7.7-Final clustering report for HORIZON-CL6-2021-

² Technische Universität Berlin. (2024). STAR4BBS D7.3 Action Plan for joint activities with other projects funded under the ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 topic (1.0). Zenodo.

³ Technische Universität Berlin. (2024). STAR4BBS D7.4 Mid-term clustering report for HORIZONCL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 (1.0). Zenodo.

⁴ Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea. (2024). STAR4BBS D7.5 First Policy Brief (1.0). Zenodo.

ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07; D7.9-Final Policy Brief); those documents will be available in Zenodo and on the website when approved.

The cooperation activities included: planning thematic area discussions, establishing a joint monitoring system, exchanging information, establishment of a joint expert advisory board, coordination in the organization of common dissemination activities. By working together and coordinating their efforts, the three projects are ensuring that their work is aligned, complementary, and contributes to the overall goal of promoting sustainability in bio-based systems. To facilitate the cooperation activities, **five thematic** inter-project teams have been established, each consisting of institutions and researchers from the three sister projects (Selection and Review of CSLs; Bio-based value chain selection and Global Trade Flows; BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System; Analysis of costs and benefits and feasibility study; Communication and dissemination of the results), seeking out synergies and cooperation opportunities among the three projects within each area. By working together through the inter-project teams and under the guidance of the Project Coordinators, the three projects are maximizing their impact towards the EU's sustainability goals.

The cluster of three sister projects established regular communication through periodic online meetings and extensive email exchange, to ensure that activities and outcomes are aligned, that various thematic areas are covered and to target potential synergies between the projects. The cluster has held more than **30 internal meetings and more than 15 with external stakeholders** (see deliverable D7.7), involving project coordinators' calls, inter-project teams' calls and meetings with the Policy Officers and Project Officers, among others. The topics discussed in these meetings were diverse, ranging from the selection of value chains and sustainability criteria to the development of a BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT).

The consolidation of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, encompassing the STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR, and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects, marked a significant stride in aligning with the objectives of the various projects. By establishing a collaborative framework and undertaking joint initiatives, the cluster effectively fostered communication and development to better address the goals set forth in the Horizon Europe call for conducting research on sustainability certification schemes in bio-based systems. The collaborative efforts underscored the clusters' commitment to strengthening the interconnectivity between the three projects. Noteworthy strategic areas of shared importance were identified, each accompanied by specified cooperation activities.

In an effort to streamline communication and receive feedback from a wider range of experts, the three projects have decided to form one **Joint Advisory Board** instead of separate boards for each project. The Joint Expert Advisory Board participated in board meetings (twice a year) and stakeholder

engagement activities organized by the cluster projects, providing feedback on research findings and bringing input relevant to the research conducted. The board meetings were organized online and on-site, with previous agreement among the cluster's Project Coordinators. The first Joint Advisory Board kick-off meeting was held on 24th of February 2023.

By aligning on the scope, KPIs, and methodology for the BMT, and by engaging with stakeholders throughout the process, the three sister projects worked together to develop a tool that has the potential to be widely adopted and used beyond the life of the projects (see subsection 2.4). The result is a comprehensive and detailed tool that can be used to assess the sustainability of biobased products and support the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU.

In liaising with other projects, STAR4BBS actively participated in the **European Commission's Horizon Results Booster programme (HRB) (Module A and B)**. Thanks to the support of an expert from ICONS, the 3 projects identified a cluster name "BIOBASEDCERT" (Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems) and specific Dissemination strategies defined in the Portfolio Dissemination Plan (PDEP).

In addition, the cluster agreed on having a dedicated space on their own project websites and a joint LinkedIn community dealing with certification of biobased feedstock/products. The joint LinkedIn community named "**Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy**" (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12968114/>), is a virtual place where all the projects involved in the field can share projects' results, goals and opinions, and where common stakeholders (e.g. certification bodies, policy makers, bioeconomy actors) can be addressed in a joint effort without competing for their attention.

7 Conclusions

The STAR4BBS project has implemented a comprehensive and dynamic communication and dissemination strategy that effectively supported its broader objective of enhancing the robustness, visibility, and uptake of sustainability certification schemes in the bio-based sector. Over the project's 36-month lifecycle, these activities significantly contributed to awareness-raising, stakeholder engagement, and policy dialogue at both national and European levels. The creation of a cohesive project identity, supported by a visual communication toolkit, website, newsletters, press releases, and active social media engagement, ensured consistent and targeted outreach to relevant audiences. Tools such as the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool and accompanying infographics, videos, and training sessions further translated scientific insights into accessible formats for a wide range of stakeholders.

Dissemination efforts were strategically aligned with project milestones, amplifying visibility through participation in high-impact events, co-creation workshops, and collaborative actions with sister projects under the BIOBASEDCERT cluster. These synergies strengthened the overall impact of STAR4BBS, allowing for knowledge transfer, joint advocacy, and the development of harmonized tools and recommendations to support the sustainability goals of the EU.

In conclusion, the communication, dissemination, and networking activities conducted under STAR4BBS have laid the groundwork for sustained stakeholder collaboration and the future exploitation of project results. They have not only showcased the project's scientific and technical achievements but also positioned STAR4BBS as a central actor in shaping credible, transparent, and effective sustainability certification systems for the bio-based economy.

“ Sustainable bio-based systems via effective certification & labelling ”

Consortium:

Unitelma Sapienza
università degli Studi di Roma

Funded by
the European Union

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

@STAR4BBS

